

Table 1: Mapping of principles and correlation between laws.

LGPD	GDPR	ADPPA	Privacy Act	CCPA
Purpose	✓ Limited Purpose tion	✓ Data Minimiza- tion	✓ Direct marketing / Use or disclosure of personal information	✓ Right to Know What Personal In- formation is Being Collected. Right to Access Personal In- formation
Adequacy	✓ Storage Limita- tion	✓ Data Minimiza- tion	✓ Use or disclo- sure of personal in- formation	✓ but not explicitly declared
Needs	✓ Data Minimiza- tion	✓ Data Minimiza- tion	✓ Collection of soli- cited personal infor- mation	✓ Right to Delete / Right to Opt Out
Open Access	✓ Right of Access	✓ Executive Res- ponsibility	✓ Access to per- sonal information / Notification of the collection of personal information	✓ Right to Know What Personal In- formation is Being Collected. Right to Access Personal In- formation
Data Quality	✓ Accuracy	✓ Right of Correc- tion	✓ Quality of per- sonal information / Correction of personal information	×
Transparency	✓ Lawfulness, fair- ness and transpa- rency	✓ Right of Transpa- rency	✓ Open and trans- parent management of personal information	✓ Right to Know What Personal In- formation is Being Collected. Right to Access Personal In- formation
Security	✓ Integrity and confidentiality	✓ Right of Data Se- curity	✓ Security of perso- nal information	✓ Security procedure res and practices
Prevention	✓ Restrictions	✓ Data Minimiza- tion	✓ Security of perso- nal information	✓ Security procedure res and practices
Non-discrimination	✓ Restrictions	✓ Data Minimiza- tion	×	✓ Right of No Re- taliation
Accountability	✓ Accountability	✓ Executive Res- ponsibility	×	✓ Right of No Re- taliation

Table 2: Mapping of LGPD principles and correlation between frameworks.

LGPD	Privacy by Design	ISO/IEC 29100
Purpose	× [23]	✓ Consent and choice / Purpose legitimacy and specification [14], [23]
Adequacy	✓ Privacy as the Default Setting [44]	✓ Collection limitation [14], [23]
Needs	✓ Proactive not Reactive; Preventive not Remedial / Privacy as Default Setting / Privacy Embedded into Design [44]	✓ Data minimization [14], [44]
Open Access	✓ Visibility and Transparency [23], [44]	✓ Individual participation and access [14]
Data Quality	✓ Proactive not Reactive; Preventive not Remedial [44]	✓ Accuracy and quality [14], [23], [44]
Transparency	✓ Visibility and Transparency [23], [44]	✓ Openness, transparency and notice [14], [23], [44]
Security	✓ End-to-End Protection [23]	✓ Information security [14], [23], [44]
Prevention	✓ Proactive not Reactive; Preventative not Remedial	✓ Privacy compliance [14]
Non-discrimination	✓ Respect for User Privacy [44]	× [14]
Accountability	× [23]	✓ Accountability [14], [23], [44]